

Novel System Of Quercetin And Its Application For Skin Disorder

Farhan khan¹, Khushboo Katharotiya^{2*}, K.Sushma², Lalit Lata Jah³ L.D Patel⁴

¹PG Student, Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

³Principal, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

⁴PG Dean, Faculty Of Pharmacy, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

*Corresponding Author: Khushboo Katharotiya

ABSTRACT

Quercetin is a plant flavonol from the flavonoid group of polyphenols with strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-proliferation activities. It possess scientifically proven anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory. The application of this compound is difficult because of poor solubility, poor availability, poor permeability, unstable in gastrointestinal tract. In these case, nanotechnology and nanoparticles provide certain advantages such as a drug half-life, lower toxicity, and specific and selective delivery over free drugs. Nanodrugs possess the capability to buildup in the tissue which might be linked to enhanced permeability and retention as well as enhanced anti-inflammation influence possessing minimal toxicity in normal tissue. This article presents information about quercetin, use in skin disorder. Different different activity of quercetin. Attention is drawn on nanotechnology, the usefulness of nanoparticles containing quercetin. Its opportunities, and also future perspective. The review article is aimed at summarizing the current state of pharmaceutical development and employment of nanotechnology in the enhancement of the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic features of quercetin as a anti-inflammation agent.

Keywords: Quercetin, Skin disorders, Topical Applications, Nano carriers

INTRODUCTION

The biggest organ in the human body, the skin is in charge of preserving internal homeostasis and controlling body temperature. The skin acts as a protective layer, preventing from pathogens of the body from external contaminants and oxidizing agents like radiation and corrosive elements that could enter internal organs. The skin has multiple antioxidant systems to protect it against external sources of oxidation, but it is constantly exposed to oxidants and inflammation. Excitatory stress that surpasses the skin's protective capacity can lead to damage to the skin[1,2]. Quercetin demonstrates antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Quercetin's anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties are critical to both neuronal survival and its ability to function as an oxidative, kinase, and cell cycle inhibitor. [3] Their effects of antioxidants on the skin, including polyphenols, vitamin-C, β -carotene and Coenzyme Q10 were investigate[4]. Its unfortunate reduced bioavailability due to its poor water solubility, which prevents it from effectively reaching its targets within the human body, explains why quercetin is useless when applied topically. Certain quercetin formulations have been investigated as highly attractive delivery routes for immune system support, skin protection against oxidation, inflammation, and photoaging, and throughout the wound healing process.[5] The majority of quercetin metabolism takes place in the intestines and liver[6] The presence of nonpolar groups in quercetin's structure results in a partition coefficient of 1.82 ± 0.32 . However, polar hydroxyl groups in quercetin reduce its ability to penetrate the skin even with this log P.[7] In order to include therapeutic compounds such as linoleic acid in nanoformulations, ethosomes and transfersomes are employed, with a focus on topical dispersion from the formulation process[8]. Additionally, asiaticoside in ultra-deformable vesicles was demonstrated to improve colloidal system. This is related to the lipid-like qualities of nanoformulations, and their small size and flexibility, which enable deep penetration. Higher skin penetration was seen for encapsulated molecules in the presence of ethanol than for liposomes, and the presence of ethanol fluidizes the liposomal bilayer, facilitating the penetration of ethosomes. Consequently, to increase topical drug distribution, quercetin is also included in several nanoformulations[9].

HISTORY OF TOPICAL PRODUCT

Since ancient times, skin delivery of poorly soluble and low bioavailable medications has been practiced extensively around the world[9]. After 1500 BC, the Greek physician Galen created the first cold cream emulsion using beeswax, water, and vegetable oil for skin treatment. Greece and other countries utilized these lotions to treat burns and wounds because they have shown strong efficacy against microbial infections[10]. They were additionally utilized by Chinese people in the past to administer mixtures of herbs as bandages and plasters. In China, plasters have therapeutic properties that include various herbs and medications, such as castor oil, moringa, and sesame seed, In 2000 BCE, astringents, diaphoretics, and protectants were utilized. Plasters have been used extensively historically to treat skin conditions. Nevertheless, when phenol skin poisoning from broken off from plasters was investigated in the 20th century, researchers were interested in medication administration by transdermal and topical methods[11]. The location of topical administration and the chemistry of the steroids, and the vehicle utilized in the formulation have all contributed to these unfavorable consequences. Over time, persistent technical progress has expanded our understanding of the drug's mechanism of percutaneous absorption and enhanced the caliber of sophisticated topical formulations. The 20th and 21st centuries saw an explosion in research that improved our understanding of skin morphology, pharmacology, toxicology, physiology, and pharmaceutical technology. One such area of study was the measurement of drug permeation from topically applied drug products that could penetrate the human stratum, epidermis corneum, and dermatomed skin[12]. Bangham pioneered the discovery of liposomes in 1965, and since then, researchers have been looking at them as the most effective way to deliver medications and physiologically active substances.[13] These spherical vesicles may carry both hydrophilic and hydrophobic medications because they resemble biological membranes. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are thought to be the next generation of delivery methods, after liposomes. SLNs have been introduced as an alternative to traditional colloidal carriers, including liposomes, emulsions, and polymeric micro- and nanoparticles. The dependability of the SLN is one of its main advantages[14]. Another development in vesicular drug delivery systems is ethosomes, which offer improved medication penetration and delivery to the deep layers of skin across a broad range of dermatological conditions. When compared to traditional liposomal formulations, Touitou and his team's ethosomes, which use ethanol instead of cholesterol as a penetration enhancer and boost medication concentration between epidermal layers, were created in 2000. The research found that the various vesicular drug delivery systems functioned differently based on their makeup. Therefore, it is preferable to use a combination of ethosomes and deformable transferases to create an elastic drug delivery system that can penetrate skin layers and more effectively pass skin membrane barriers[15].

SKIN TARGET AND BARRIERS

Skin has several vital functions, including regulating body temperature, shielding the body from the outside world, and removing water from the body. The stratum corneum (SC) layer of skin has physical barriers to topical product absorption as well as skin morphological characteristics. The epidermis and dermis are two significant viable physical barriers found in the skin in addition to the nonviable physical barriers. The flat, hexagon-shaped corneocytes that make up the outermost layer of the epidermis are 40 μm in diameter, up to 1 μm broad, and parallel to the skin's surface. The outermost layer of SC, known as the stratum disjunction, or superficial zone, serves as a skin barrier and sheds and reforms continuously, taking, for example, 21 days for the back of the hands and 7 days for the forehead[16]. The interactions between topical formulations and the dynamic barrier SC are what determine how drugs are delivered. The stratum basale's tight junctions between corneocytes and their hook-shaped overlapping ends can occasionally delay or lengthen the period between stratum disjunction. In topical carriers, water plays a crucial role in modulating the SC layer. Moisturizers work to stop water from evaporating from the skin. Corneocyte undulation was reduced by moist, pliable, and thick SC in comparison to dry SC[17]. Lipids and proteins in the SC layer combine to form an assembly resembling mortar when the proteins in the layer form disulfide bonds with one another. Corneocytes are surrounded by these protein bricks, which provide them biochemical strength, and the lipid mortar structure serves as a functional barrier. The medicine must be able to pass through the functional barrier of SC lipids and reach the corneocyte brick in order to be absorbed via the cutaneous route[18]. The corneocytes are long, flat cells that are often up to 50 μm in length and 1.5 μm in thickness. They have no nucleus and are made up of around 80–90% keratin and 20–20% lipid inside of a cornified cell envelope that is about 10 μm thick. The outer layer of corneocytes is surrounded by a protein/lipid polymer structure called the cornified cell envelope, which forms immediately below the cytoplasmic membrane[19].

TYPES OF SKIN DISORDER

Between 15% and 20% percent of family have skin issues. However, little attention is usually paid to how skin diseases impact patients emotional well-being. Improvements in both general and specialized quality-of-life devices have led to a better understanding of the impact that skin disorders have on both adults and children [20]. There are various types of skin disorders are reported as mentioned below:

Acne vulgaris

Acne is a condition affecting the skin's pilosebaceous unit, which are hair follicles connected to oil glands. The face, neck, upper chest, shoulders, and back contain the highest density of pilosebaceous units and are the areas where acne is most frequent. Categorization of acne, scarring, rosacea, chloracne, infantile acne, inversa acne, acne associated with polycystic ovarian syndrome, and drug-induced acne have all been discussed previously. A common inflammatory skin condition is acne vulgaris. Although it is widely believed to be a self-limiting adolescent illness, it often remains a while into adulthood. Ninety percent of teens have acne, and fifty percent of those still have problems as adults [21].

Alopecia areata

Alopecia Areata is a chronic inflammatory illness that causes temporary loss of hair. Alopecia areata is categorized as a tissue-restricted autoimmune illness as it has a correlation with other autoimmune disorders in the afflicted individual and their family circulating antibodies against In individuals with Alopecia areata, follicular components are found more frequently[22].

Ichthyosis

The word "ichthyosis" is used to describe a broad category of dermatological disorders characterized by scaly, erythematous skin and abnormalities in the function of the epidermal barrier. According to the most recent consensus categorization, there are two basic types of ichthyosis: nonsyndromic forms, which possess only symptoms on the skin, and syndromic forms, which show symptoms in other organs. It is open to receiving or gaining ichthyoses aquired forms can result from several underlying reasons, including but not limited to malignancies, autoimmune illnesses, nutritional problems, and medicines.[23]

Skin cancer

Skin cancer, with a lifetime risk nearly equal to all other malignancies combined, is the most frequent neoplasm among Caucasians in the United States. less common within darkly pigmented individuals than in Caucasians with light skin, skin cancer can be associated with high inflation rates of morbidity as well as mortality. The primary reason why darker-skinned populations have lower rates of cutaneous cancers is because of photoprotection from higher levels of epidermal melanin, which gives black people an innate UV protection factor of up to 13.4.[24]

Rosacea

The core face convexities of the forehead, nose, cheeks, and chin are most affected by the well-known chronic cutaneous condition rosacea. It is categorized as a syndrome, or typology, to the best of our knowledge, involving a variety of combinations of cutaneous symptoms such as eye lesions, erythema, telangiectasia, edema, papules, pustules, and rhinophyma. Macular redness of the ears, scalp, neck, upper chest, and lateral facial contours may be indications of erythemato-telangiectatic rosacea (ETR). The pathophysiology of rosacea remains uncertain. There are many more potential reasons, but those that have been suggested include a compromised innate immune system, neurogenic inflammation, neurovascular dysregulation, and UV damage[25].

Vitiligo

A multifactorial disease is vitiligo. In vitiligo skin, there are no active melanocytes. that the cause of this loss of melanocytes that can be identified histochemically is destruction. The disease is characterized by a complete absence of melanocytes and an acquired, idiopathic, progressive, confined hypomelanosis of the skin and hair. It is widespread and depigmenting to the skin. Vitiligo patients usually have higher anxiety scores, sadness, adjustment disorders, obsessive symptoms, and hypochondria[26].

Eczema

Eczema is a long-term, inflammatory skin condition that has a strong hereditary component and autoimmune pathogenic characteristics. Skin conditions like eczema have been linked to a number of illnesses. It may also affect joints. Although no specific immunogen has been found, Eczema is an immune-mediated condition with a hereditary propensity. T lymphocytes, dendritic cells, and cytokines are detectable[27].

ACTIVITY OF QUERCETIN IN SKIN DISORDER

Anti-Oxidant Activity

Quercetin's capacity to lessen oxidative damage from metals and non-metals is linked to its free 3-OH (hydroxyl) substituent. Quercetin scavenges free radicals, which reduces inflammation. Due to its capacity to bind transition metal ions and scavenge free radicals, Quercetin is regarded as a potent antioxidant. It has been proven that quercetin is a more effective O₂-scavenger than NO

when O₂–is increased in blood vessel smooth muscle. The excellent antioxidant activity of quercetin helps shield the human body from oxidative stress damage [28].

Anti-Inflammatory

Quercetin has been shown in in vivo studies to have anti-inflammatory properties. Because glycoside derivatives are less absorbed through the skin's surface, they are inefficient against topical irritation [29].

Anti-Microbial Activity

When it comes to several bacterial strains that impact the gastrointestinal, respiratory, urinary, and integumentary systems, quercetin demonstrates antibacterial properties. The hydroxyl groups in quercetin are present. Quercetin's antibacterial action against oral pathogens shown its bactericidal efficacy against germs linked to dental caries. Certain quercetin derivatives were more effective against Gram-negative bacteria than Gram-positive ones in terms of antibacterial activity[30].

Anti-Fungal

Certain harmful fungal species may be inhibited by quercetin. Quercetin stops the growth of fungus and causes cell death by causing oxidative stress and changing the structure of the cell walls of fungi. Quercetin was successfully found to possess antifungal effects against both *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus niger* (16–64 μM). Quercetin is increasingly effective against resistant fungal infections. Two main mechanisms are the breakdown of the plasma membrane and the suppression of protein, nucleic acid, and mitochondrial production [31].

Anti-Viral

The antiviral properties of quercetin and its derivatives have long been researched. Quercetin and its derivatives shown antiviral properties in vitro against several viruses, such as the respiratory viruses caused by the Sindbis virus, the poliovirus, the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), and the Mayaravirus. Quercetin provides mice infected with the Mengo virus with some degree of protection against fatal infections when given orally in vivo. Quercetin improved acyclovir's antiviral efficacy against herpesviruses in vitro. In vivo, quercetin helped treat and prevent individuals with early respiratory tract infections, particularly those with COVID-19, when combined with vitamin C. Quercetin was found to possess antiviral characteristics against certain rhinovirus serotypes, Coxsackievirus, Poliovirus, Echovirus and among other viruses [32].

Immunomodulation

Quercetin is an effective immunomodulatory substance because of its direct modulatory effects on various immune cells, cytokines, and other immune chemicals. It also has indirect effects that are changed by antioxidant and anti-inflammatory processes. Quercetin affects the quantity of cytokines produced. Quercetin is widely recognized for stabilizing mast cells and altering their activity, which controls inflammation and immunity. Quercetin suppresses immunological responses in dendritic cells [33].

Wound Healing

Quercetin has also wound healing mechanism by revealing different signaling pathway. It promotes proliferation even migration of fibroblasts to enhance wound healing. The development of granulation tissue marks the beginning of the healing process. Inflammation is the primary cause of wound-healing complications in most instances. The process consists of four distinct and overlapping phases: proliferation, inflammation, and hemostasis. The wound contraction tissue is then remodeled or breaks down to aid in the restoration of the skin's barrier function.[34]

NOVEL SYSTEM OF QUERCETIN

Nanoformulations

Quercetin is a difficult chemical to give because of its poor solubility, low hydrophilicity (log P of 1.81), gastrointestinal instability, significant first pass metabolism, and little absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Quercetin belongs to BCS class II compounds. fewer than 17% in rats and fewer than 2% in humans have been reported to have oral bioavailability of this substance. The effectiveness of possible therapeutic compounds, which otherwise have some limits, has been claimed to be improved by approaches based on nanoformulations for their distribution. Quercetin has been reported to be delivered by a variety of methods, including liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles, nanoparticles, and microemulsions, for use in aging and neurodegenerative diseases,

among other conditions. The therapeutic efficacy of nano-encapsulated quercetin in arsenic oxide-induced ROS-mediated oxidative damage in hepatocytes and brain cells was evaluated by oral administration prior to arsenite treatment. The results showed an improvement in antioxidant levels in the liver and brain. Quercetin demonstrated increased relative oral bioavailability by 5.71-fold and drug release for 48 hours *in vivo*. With a particle size of around 400 nm, QR-LeciPlex demonstrated good colloidal stability. The QR-LeciPlex demonstrated a very high QR encapsulation efficiency (>90%) and a zeta potential larger than +30 mV [35].

Polymeric Delivery Systems

Quercetin nanoparticles were made using the biocompatible polymer which dissolves at higher pH values but is stable under acidic circumstances (pH<5.5). As a result, this polymer may be utilized to hold components in place inside of highly acidic environments like the stomach or within commercial items that are acidic yet release them into the small intestine, which is neutral biocompatible nanoparticles with an encapsulation effectiveness of 79.78% and a modest size (<200 nm). Over the course of 12 hours at pH 7.4, an *in vitro* drug release investigation revealed a total quantity of 67.28% release of Quercetin [36].

Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), a type of submicron particulate drug delivery technique that has attracted a lot of interest, are an alternative carrier system to traditional colloidal dispersion. Other systems that fall under this category include polymeric microparticles, nanoparticles, emulsions, and liposomes. The medicine was either disseminated or encased in natural or synthesized solid lipids, which were then utilized as carriers to create solid colloidal particles. The sizes of the particles range from around 10 to 1000 nm [37]. Several advantages of the system include its controlled release, high bioavailability, high biocompatibility, and lack of problems when administered by oral, intravenous, pulmonary, or transdermal routes [38].

Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System

The self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS), because of its simplicity in formulation and assessment, is a potential technology to increase the rate and extent of absorption of weakly water-soluble substances. SEDDS formulation is an isotropic combination of oil, co-surfactant, surfactant, and medication that can emulsify with water when gently shaken, much like the gastrointestinal tract. Because of the drug's solubilized state and the vast interfacial area provided by the droplets' tiny particle size, the spontaneous emulsion formation *in vivo* promotes a greater rate and extent of absorption. Due to the fact that many of the excipients used in SEDDS are not solids at room temperature, SEDDS is typically only available in liquid dosage forms. This has several drawbacks, including instability issues, incompatibility, drug leakage, precipitation, etc. Solid-Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems (S-SEDDS) are more efficient than traditional liquid SEDDS because of the benefits of solid dosage forms. S-SEDDS combines the benefits of solid dosage forms with those of SEDDS, such as improved patient compliance, ease of process control, cheap production costs, and excellent stability. Quercetin's water solubility was examined at varied concentrations (0.1, 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 mM) in relation to many generations of dendrimers, namely G0, G1, G2, and G3. After that, PAMAM was able to effectively implement it dendrimers, and their stability, surface shape, size, size distribution, and effectiveness of incorporation were assessed [39].

Quercetin-loaded Hydrogels

Hydrophilic polymeric networks, or hydrogels, have the ability to change or regulate drug release in addition to having a high moisture content, biocompatibility, soft and flexible texture, and mechanical qualities like those of biological tissues. Hydrogels may be made with both synthetic and natural biopolymers; typically, hybrid matrices made of two polymers from each source successfully balance the hydrogel's properties. In actuality, although artificial polymer-based hydrogels are easier to remove from skin and have better mechanical qualities when swelled, single biopolymer-based hydrogels are challenging to tune in terms of hydrophilicity, stiffness, and elasticity. A type of emulsion known as a nanoemulsion has homogeneous droplet sizes between 20 and 200 nm, which are incredibly small [40].

Nanoemulgel

The topical administration of quercetin using nanotechnology improves its solubility, increases skin permeability, boosts its physicochemical stability, and offers a controlled and sustained release profile. The kind Nanoemulgel formulations are used in the topical administration of quercetin by nanotechnology. The nanoemulgel formulation was selected due to its ability to distribute lipophilic medicines and its resistance to water solubility. Drug encapsulation with nanoemulgel is very efficient as compared to alternative lipid-based techniques, and it can be prepared without the need for solvents and with minimal energy. The gel basis of the nanoemulgel will release oil droplets when it comes into contact with the skin. Next, the oil droplets penetrating the stratum corneum molecules without passing through the nanoemulsion's hydrophilic phase will directly deliver the medicine. The optimized nanoemulsion had a droplet size of 16.71 nm and a low polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.015, along with a negative zeta potential of -20.6 mV [41].

Future Prospects of Quercetin

Quercetin novel drug delivery systems can increased bioavailability results in an improvement its efficacy. Drug resistance risks can be avoided and dosages can be decreased when bioenhancer and medication are combined. Reducing the dosage can also lower the treatment's cost, making it more affordable. Reduced dose will lessen the likelihood of adverse medication reactions, side effects, and drug toxicity.

Nanocarriers of Quercetin For Topical Drug Delivery

Nano Formulation	Preparation Technique	Inference	Reference
PLGA polymer	Single emulsion (o/w)–solvent evaporation technique	A poly lactide-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) polymer based nanoparticles of quercetin with a view to improve its aqueous solubility and examine the effect on its antioxidant and diuretic properties	36
Lipid nanocarriers	Hot solvent diffusion method	Development of qu-loaded nanocarriers (nes) is a promising approach to improve the drug oral bioavailability	38
Polyamidoamine(pamam) dendrimer	Biotech cellulose ester dialysis membrane	It was observed that both generation and the respective concentrations of pamam dendrimers showed potential positive effects on solubility enhancement of quercetin	39
Liposomes	Film Hydration Method	Increasing Dppc Concentration And Lipid Ratio Significantly Enhanced Qu Entrapment.	42
Microsponge	Quasiemulsion solvent diffusion.	The physical description of a microsponge formulation with a Gel-3 covering shows that it has a higher loading efficiency and yield	43
Loaded nanosponges	Emulsion solvent diffusion method	Prepare quercetin loaded nanosponges topical gel to enhance the solubility and efficacy of the drug	44
magnetic core-shell	modified Massart method	exhibiting enhanced solubility and stability in physiological media, as evidenced by the loading capacity, entrapment efficiency	45
Ethosomes	Thin-film hydration method	To enhance penetration and bioavailability of quercetin using transdermal ethosomal gel	46
Iron Oxide	Chemical coprecipitation method.	It showed that quercetin could prevent weight loss due to the SPION	47
Phytosomes	Thin layer hydration method	Formulation to produce lipophilic molecular complex to improve absorption and bioavailability of phytoconstituent.	48

REFERENCE

1. Li H, Zhao X, Ma Y, Zhai G, Li L, Lou H. Enhancement of gastrointestinal absorption of quercetin by solid lipid nanoparticles. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2009 Feb 10;133(3):238-44.
2. Sander CS, Chang H, Salzman S, Müller CS, Ekanayake-Mudiyanselage S, Elsner P, Thiele JJ. Photoaging is associated with protein oxidation in human skin in vivo. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*. 2002 Apr 1;118(4):618-25.
3. Bonina F, Lanza M, Montenegro L, Puglisi C, Tomaino A, Trombetta D, Castelli F, Saija A. Flavonoids as potential protective agents against photo-oxidative skin damage. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 1996 Dec 6;145(1-2):87-94.
4. Hoppe U, Bergemann J, Diembeck W, Ennen J, Gohla S, Harris I, Jacob J, Kielholz J, Mei W, Pollet D, Schachtschabel D. Coenzyme Q₁₀, a cutaneous antioxidant and energizer. *Biofactors*. 1999 Jan 1;9(2-4):371-8.
5. Vicentini FT, He T, Shao Y, Fonseca MJ, Verri Jr WA, Fisher GJ, Xu Y. Quercetin inhibits UV irradiation-induced inflammatory cytokine production in primary human keratinocytes by suppressing NF- κ B pathway. *Journal of dermatological science*. 2011 Mar 1;61(3):162-8.

6. Harwood M, Danielewska-Nikiel B, Borzelleca JF, Flamm GW, Williams GM, Lines TC. A critical review of the data related to the safety of quercetin and lack of evidence of in vivo toxicity, including lack of genotoxic/carcinogenic properties. *Food and chemical toxicology*. 2007 Nov 1;45(11):2179-205.
7. Rothwell JA, Day AJ, Morgan MR. Experimental determination of octanol– water partition coefficients of quercetin and related flavonoids. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*. 2005 Jun 1;53(11):4355-60.
8. Celia C, Cilurzo F, Trapasso E, Cosco D, Fresta M, Paolino D. Ethosomes® and transfersomes® containing linoleic acid: physicochemical and technological features of topical drug delivery carriers for the potential treatment of melasma disorders. *Biomedical microdevices*. 2012 Feb;14:119-30.
9. Liu D, Hu H, Lin Z, Chen D, Zhu Y, Hou S, Shi X. Quercetin deformable liposome: preparation and efficacy against ultraviolet B induced skin damages in vitro and in vivo. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*. 2013 Oct 5;127:8-17.
10. Dlova NC, Ollengo MA. Traditional and ethnobotanical dermatology practices in Africa. *Clinics in Dermatology*. 2018 May 1;36(3):353-62.
11. Fratini F, Cilia G, Turchi B, Felicioli A. Beeswax: A minireview of its antimicrobial activity and its application in medicine. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2016 Sep 1;9(9):839-43.
12. Chien, Y. W. Development of Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems. *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.* 1987, 13 (4–5), 589–651
13. Bangham, A. D. Surrogate cells or Trojan horses. The discovery of liposomes. *BioEssays*. 1995, 17 (12), 1081–1088
14. Müller RH, Mäder K, Gohla S. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) for controlled drug delivery—a review of the state of the art. *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*. 2000 Jul 3;50(1):161-77.
15. Touitou E, Dayan N, Bergelson L, Godin B, Eliaz M. Ethosomes—novel vesicular carriers for enhanced delivery: characterization and skin penetration properties. *Journal of controlled release*. 2000 Apr 3;65(3):403-18.
16. Song CK, Balakrishnan P, Shim CK, Chung SJ, Chong S, Kim DD. A novel vesicular carrier, transethosome, for enhanced skin delivery of voriconazole: characterization and in vitro/in vivo evaluation. *Colloids and surfaces B: biointerfaces*. 2012 Apr 1;92:299-304.
17. Wepf R, Richter T, Biel SS, Schlu H. Multimodal imaging of skin structures: imagining imaging of the skin. *InBioengineering of the Skin 2006 Sep 27, 77-96, CRC Press*.
18. Roberts MS, Cheruvu HS, Mangion SE, Alinaghi A, Benson HA, Mohammed Y, Holmes A, van der Hoek J, Pastore M, Grice JE. Topical drug delivery: History, percutaneous absorption, and product development. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*. 2021 Oct 1;177:113929.
19. Patel V, Sharma OP, Mehta T. Nanocrystal: a novel approach to overcome skin barriers for improved topical drug delivery. *Expert opinion on drug delivery*. 2018 Apr 3;15(4):351-68.
20. Morgan VA. Skin disease in general practice. *Australasian journal of dermatology*. 1992 Aug 1;33(2).
21. Webster GF. The pathophysiology of acne. *Cutis*. 2005 Aug 1;76(2 Suppl):4-7.
22. Safavi KH, Muller SA, Suman VJ, Moshell AN, Melton III LJ. Incidence of alopecia areata in Olmsted County, Minnesota, 1975 through 1989. *InMayo Clinic Proceedings 1995 Jul 1, Vol. 70, No. 7, 628-633, Elsevier*.
23. Oji V, Tadani G, Akiyama M, Bardou CB, Bodemer C, Bourrat E, Coudiere P, DiGiovanna JJ, Elias P, Fischer J, Fleckman P. Revised nomenclature and classification of inherited ichthyoses: results of the First Ichthyosis Consensus Conference in Sorèze 2009. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*. 2010 Oct 1;63(4):607-41.
24. Hu S. Are we overlooking skin cancer in ethnic minorities. *population*. 2011;12:14.
25. Van Zuuren EJ, Fedorowicz Z, Carter B, van der Linden MM, Charland L. Interventions for rosacea. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2015(4).

26. Daneshpazhooh M, Mostofizadeh G M, Behjati J, Akhyani M, Robati RM. Anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody and vitiligo: a controlled study. *BMC dermatology*. 2006 Dec;6:1-5.
27. Griffiths CE, Barker JN. Pathogenesis and clinical features of psoriasis. *The Lancet*. 2007 Jul 21;370(9583):263-71.
28. Lopez-Lopez G, Moreno L, Cogolludo A, Galisteo M, Ibarra M, Duarte J, Lodi F, Tamargo J, Perez-Vizcaino F. Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging and NO protecting effects of quercetin and their biological significance in vascular smooth muscle. *Molecular pharmacology*. 2004 Apr 1;65(4):851-9.
29. Lin CF, Leu YL, Al-Suwayeh SA, Ku MC, Hwang TL, Fang JY. Anti-inflammatory activity and percutaneous absorption of quercetin and its polymethoxylated compound and glycosides: The relationships to chemical structures. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2012 Dec 18;47(5):857-64.
30. Osonga FJ, Akgul A, Miller RM, Eshun GB, Yazgan I, Akgul A, Sadik OA. Antimicrobial activity of a new class of phosphorylated and modified flavonoids. *ACS omega*. 2019 Jul 30;4(7):12865-71.
31. Yin J, Peng X, Lin J, Zhang Y, Zhang J, Gao H, Tian X, Zhang R, Zhao G. Quercetin ameliorates *Aspergillus fumigatus* keratitis by inhibiting fungal growth, toll-like receptors and inflammatory cytokines. *International Immunopharmacology*. 2021 Apr 1;93:107435.
32. Agrawal PK, Agrawal C, Blunden G. Quercetin: antiviral significance and possible COVID-19 integrative considerations. *Natural Product Communications*. 2020 Dec;15(12):1934578X20976293.
33. Chirumbolo S. The role of quercetin, flavonols and flavones in modulating inflammatory cell function. *Inflammation & Allergy-Drug Targets (Formerly Current Drug Targets-Inflammation & Allergy)(Discontinued)*. 2010 Sep 1;9(4):263-85.
34. Mi Y, Zhong L, Lu S, Hu P, Pan Y, Ma X, Yan B, Wei Z, Yang G. Quercetin promotes cutaneous wound healing in mice through Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2022 May 23;290:115066.
35. Date AA, Nagarsenker MS, Patere S, Dhawan V, Gude RP, Hassan PA, Aswal V, Steiniger F, Thamm J, Fahr A. Lecithin-based novel cationic nanocarriers (Leciplex) II: improving therapeutic efficacy of quercetin on oral administration. *Molecular Pharmaceutics*. 2011 Jun 6;8(3):716-26.
36. Baksi R, Singh DP, Borse SP, Rana R, Sharma V, Nivsarkar M. In vitro and in vivo anticancer efficacy potential of Quercetin loaded polymeric nanoparticles. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2018 Oct 1;106:1513-26.
37. Müller RH, Mäder K, Gohla S. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) for controlled drug delivery—a review of the state of the art. *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*. 2000 Jul 3;50(1):161-77.
38. Hädrich G, Monteiro SO, Rodrigues MR, de Lima VR, Putaux JL, Bidone J, Teixeira HF, Muccillo-Baisch AL, Dora CL. Lipid-based nanocarrier for quercetin delivery: system characterization and molecular interactions studies. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. 2016 Jul 2;42(7):1165-73.
39. Madaan K, Lather V, Pandita D. Evaluation of polyamidoamine dendrimers as potential carriers for quercetin, a versatile flavonoid. *Drug delivery*. 2016 Jan 2;23(1):254-62.
40. Chellapa P, Mohamed AT, Keleb EI, Elmahgoubi A, Eid AM, Issa YS, Elmarzugi NA. Nanoemulsion and nanoemulgel as a topical formulation. *IOSR J Pharm*. 2015 Oct;5(10):43-7.
41. Algahtani MS, Ahmad MZ, Ahmad J. Nanoemulgel for improved topical delivery of retinyl palmitate: formulation design and stability evaluation. *Nanomaterials*. 2020 Apr 28;10(5):848.
42. Tefas LR, Muntean DM, Vlase L, Porfire AS, Achim M, Tomuță I. Quercetin-loaded liposomes: formulation optimization through a D-optimal experimental design. *Farmacia*. 2015 Jan 1;63(1):126-33.
43. Muruganantham V, Venkateswarlu BS, Chinraj V. Design and Evaluation of Isolated Herbal Extracts of Aloin, Proanthocyanidin, Quercetin Loaded Microsponge as Sunscreen Gel. *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences*. 2022 May;11(2):357.
44. Sujitha YS, Muzib YI. Formulation and optimization of quercetin loaded nanosponges topical gel: Ex vivo, pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic studies. *Int. J. Appl. Pharm*. 2019 Sep 1;11:156-65.

45. Halevas E, Mavroidi B, Nday CM, Tang J, Smith GC, Boukos N, Litsardakis G, Pelecanou M, Salifoglou A. Modified magnetic core-shell mesoporous silica nano-formulations with encapsulated quercetin exhibit anti-amyloid and antioxidant activity. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*. 2020 Dec 1;213:111271.
46. Ramadan D, Anwar E, Harahap Y. In vitro Penetration and Bioavailability of Novel Transdermal Quercetin-loaded Ethosomal Gel. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2017 Nov 1;79(6).
47. Najafabadi, Rezvan Enteshari, et al. Quercetin prevents body weight loss due to the using of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles in rat. *Advanced biomedical research*.7.2018.
48. Rasaei, Solmaz, et al. Nano phytosomes of quercetin: A promising formulation for fortification of food products with antioxidants." *Pharmaceutical sciences* 20.3.2014: 96-101.